

Educational Status and Transgender Heterogeneity: An intersectional study of Select Transgender Autobiographies

S.A.Annie Swetha M.A, MPhil, NET
Assistant Professor, Department of English,
Stella Maris College
Chennai-600086

Abstract:

Education plays a major role in defining and differentiating the lives of individuals—in this case, trans individuals. In light of this, the homogeneous othering of trans identity can be subjected to criticism, especially when considering the impact of education. An intersectional approach to the categories of gender identity and education provides a more pluralistic perspective, offering a nuanced understanding of the diverse experiences within trans identities. This study emphasises the need to recognise the heterogeneity within transgender communities in educational contexts, highlighting how diverse gender identities and lived experiences demand inclusive, responsive, and non-uniform pedagogical approaches.

Key words: Intersectionality, Education, Transgender Heterogeneity

Intersectionality and Gender Equity in Academia

The educational experiences of transgender individuals are far from monolithic. Within this community, there exists a significant variation in educational attainment, shaped by multiple intersecting factors such as socioeconomic status, geographic location, access to resources, and societal attitudes toward gender nonconformity. While some transgender individuals may pursue and achieve higher education, many others face barriers such as discrimination, stigmatisation, and a lack of family or institutional support that hinder their academic progress. This variation is further compounded by cultural, regional, and class-

based differences, particularly in contexts like India, where transgender people's educational opportunities can be severely restricted. Recognising the heterogeneity within the transgender community in terms of educational qualifications is critical for developing tailored, inclusive policies that can address the unique challenges faced by different groups within this diverse population.

The objective of this study is to explore the intersection of gender (the transgender status of the three protagonists) and education, by tracing out their different educational backgrounds and how it contributes to the heterogeneous nature of their trans identities (Revathi, a school dropout; Laxmi, a postgraduate; and Manobi, an MPhil Scholar). The primary texts chosen for this study are: A. Revathi, *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story*, Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's *Me Hijra, Me Laxmi* and Manobi Bandyopadhyay's *A Gift of Goddess Lakshmi*. The lived educational experiences of the protagonists are centred on two major themes: positive versus negative educational environment as well as career opportunities versus stigmatised professions. The confluence of both oppressed and privileged identities of the protagonists due to the intersection of the above markers will destabilise the homogenous assumptions about their transgender identities.

Is Education Truly Gender-Neutral?

Education influences society by socialising the individuals; that is education processes or transforms individuals into social beings. In accordance to this belief, in the work "School climate for transgender youth: A mixed method investigation of student experiences and school responses," it is stated that education is an organized network responsible for socializing individuals into performing normative roles in the society, especially with regard to gender norms (McGuire et al. 1176).

Gender socialisation refers to the process of learning the social attributes of one's gender (McGuire et al. 1177) through social institutions, such as family, church, school and mass-media. Education, in particular, alters or teaches the way an individual has to act, perform and present themselves to the society (McGuire et al. 1177). Accordingly, the prevailing studies on education are organised around the perception that education is a dominant social agent responsible for transmitting values, skills and behaviours that are considered appropriate by the society. This argument can be backed using the following examples.

Louis Althusser's work *Ideology and Ideological State Apparatuses* (1970) considers family, education, religion and media as the leading ISAs. These ISAs foster an ideology that coincides with the desires of the state. The educational ISA, in particular, is criticised by Althusser for interpellating the younger generation into accepting the dominant ideologies. He states,

[The Ideological State Apparatus] takes children from every class at infant-school age, and then for years, the years in which the child is most 'vulnerable', squeezed between the family ISA and the educational ISA, it drums into them, whether it uses new or old methods, a certain amount of know-how wrapped in the ruling ideology or simply the ruling ideology in its pure state. (Althusser 147)

This notion is further elucidated in the work "Power and Conformity in Today's Schools" by Justin Saldan, which discusses how educational institutions interpellate individuals into performing acceptable roles, such as to prefer heteronormative gender roles. In short, the institution of education supports the continuity of thoughts, morals, values and other tenets that the culture considers important (Saldan 3). Therefore, the goal of the educational system is not only the cognitive development of learners but also the maintenance of power relationships, in terms of heteronormative gender behaviours, class

hierarchy and so on. Accordingly, social agents, such as the educational institutions, tune individuals in ways that prescribe and enforce their thinking in specific ways, regarding their identities, relationships with other individuals, and their connections to social institutions.

Likewise, Higgins in his article “LGBT Ireland Study: An Exploration of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender and Intersex Lives in the Republic of Ireland” points out how education is a significant social marker responsible for socialising individuals in specific skills and values in a society (Higgins 77-78). He further states that education is a socialising agent responsible for transforming the individual identity into a collective identity.

The societal construction of individual identities can be better understood in the words of Sara Salih, who in her essay “On Judith Butler and Performativity” (2007) describes the process of identity formation as the indoctrination of a repetitive set of acts that are unconsciously transmitted to the individual via socializing agents like education, and as a result, the individual acts out or performs their appropriate, socially acceptable roles (Salih 56).

The formation of social identities is further explored in the work *The Subject and Power* (1982) by Foucault, who suggests how individual identities as subjects and agents are formed in private and semi-private social institutions, such as families and schools. He further claims that these traditional institutions indoctrinate individuals into accepting different forms of subordination, such as heterosexuality, racism and class oppression. Therefore, educational institutions turn out to be a heteronormative space, intolerant towards the existence of non-heteronormative gender identities. The report “National School Climate Survey: The experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender youth in our nation’s school” confirms the following:

Schools nationwide are hostile environments for a distressing number of LGBT students, the overwhelming majority of whom routinely hear anti-LGBT language and

experience victimization and discrimination at school. As a result, many LGBT students avoid school activities or miss school entirely. (Kosciw et al. 494)

These form the widely accepted discourse, which labels educational institutions as a socializing agent responsible for promoting heteronormative gender preferences among the younger generation. However, it is also important to notice the heterogeneity prevalent in educational institutions. Not all educational institutions can be considered as a space which hinders the formation of a positive identity in case of gender deviants. While it is true that many LGBT's are prone to homophobic and transphobic bullying at educational institutions, the existence of queer friendly education cannot be discarded or silenced.

Education and Economic Mobility in Trans Narratives

Accordingly, in India, the emergence of trans narratives—such as Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's *Me Hijra, Me Laxmi* and Manobi Bandyopadhyay's *A Gift of Goddess Lakshmi*—marks a significant step in asserting the rights and dignity of the transgender community. These autobiographies not only advocate for transgender rights but also highlight the urgent need for inclusive educational and counseling facilities tailored to the specific needs of the community. As rightly said by Revathi, author of *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story*

“ We want to live as women, and if we are granted the facilities that will enable us to do so, we'll live as other women do. We are not born to beg or do sex work. Circumstances, faulty laws and social hatred have left us with no course but to beg or do sex work.” (Revathi 262)

This highlights how the lack of education and limited access to resources forced Revathi into stigmatised forms of livelihood such as sex work and begging. Laxmi Narayan Tripathi's formal education and postgraduate degree in Bharatnatyam enabled her to build a public career as a dancer and activist. Similarly, Manobi Bandyopadhyay's academic

achievements led her to become India's first transgender college principal. In contrast, A. Revathi's experience as a school dropout limited her economic options, pushing her into sex work and begging. These narratives show that education is not just a tool for knowledge but a crucial determinant of economic agency and social inclusion for transgender individuals.

Thus the educational backgrounds of Revathi, Laxmi Narayan Tripathi, and Manobi Bandyopadhyay reveal the diverse and unequal experiences within the transgender community, highlighting how access to education can significantly shape life trajectories and opportunities.

Intersectionality and the Diversity of Transgender Experiences

Applying an intersectional framework allows us to recognise that transgender experiences are not homogeneous, especially when intersected with educational status. For instance, Revathi, a school dropout, was forced into sex work and begging—realities faced by many hijras due to limited access to formal education and employment opportunities. In contrast, Laxmi Narayan Tripathi completed her schooling at Smt Sulochanadevi Singhanian School, earned a degree in arts from Mithibai College, and a postgraduate degree in Bharatnatyam, which enabled her to build a sustainable livelihood. Similarly, Manobi Bandyopadhyay, a postgraduate and the first transgender college principal in India, carved out a career in academia, serving as an associate professor and later as the principal of Krishnagar Women's College.

These contrasting trajectories raise an important research question: Is it right to treat transgender experiences as monolithic, particularly in terms of educational access and outcomes? The clear disparities suggest otherwise. Therefore, intersectionality emerges as an apt analytical method, offering a nuanced understanding of how gender identity, education, class, and caste collectively shape the lived realities of transgender individuals in India.

Using the above-mentioned questions of relevance, the researcher has selected the following autobiographies: A. Revathi's *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story*, Laxminarayan Tripathi's *Me Hijra, Me Laxmi* and Manobi Bandyopadhyay's *A Gift of Goddess Lakshmi* to show the diverse nature of trans identities. With the aid of these narratives, the study intends to critique the homogenous categorization of trans narratives. It intends to analyse the flaw of reading the selected texts using a binary structure: the heteronormative Indian society versus 'the collective other' (Indian transgenders).

Most studies conducted on these primary texts tend to juxtapose transgender struggle as a collective whole versus the heteronormative attitude of the society. However, the complex inequality operating within the community is often neglected. Despite the three protagonists Revathi, Manobi and Laxmi differ in terms of their families, educational experiences, class status and so on, there is an increasing tendency to homogenise or reduce their experiences into the collective category of Indian transgenders. In a nutshell, the objective of this study is to show how the identity of the three trans women protagonists (Revathi, Manobi and Laxmi) is constructed in multiple ways and therefore irreducible and heterogeneous in nature.

For instance, the article "Making Her-story: Review of A Gift of Goddess Lakshmi, Manobi Bandyopadhyay's memoir" by Aishwarya Gupta asserts the life story of Manobi by examining the struggle faced by an educated transgender in patriarchal society. However, the point that education has created a marked difference between the trajectory of Manobi's life and that of other transgenders is not emphasised.

Similarly, the researches done on Revathi's autobiography analyse the patriarchal labelling of *hijras* as the 'other'. They use Revathi's autobiography as an effective tool to condemn unjust society. Writers like Mondal Mousim, Gayathri Prabhu, Divya and Nithin Mayanth criticise the marginalised position of the *hijras* in a democratic country like India.

They also make a claim on how this ‘in-between state’ is a powerful position to subvert patriarchal domination. Along the same lines, Gaythri Prabhu and Nithin Mayanth argue on the authenticity of life narratives, which showcase the emotional trauma faced by their community. However, all these works fail to understand that the experience of Revathi, a *hijra*, has also to do with her being a Tamil, poorly qualified, fair skinned, feminine and underprivileged *hijra*. Therefore, it is one-dimensional to limit a Revathi’s experience to the broad category of Indian transgenders, as individuals perform many social roles and constitute multiple identities.

Moving to the studies conducted on the writings of Laxminarayan Tripathi, Rajorshi Das in her article, “Representation and Categorization: Understanding the Hijra and Transgender Identities through Personal Narratives” considers autobiographical writings as a legitimising tool as for queer activism in India. Likewise, Paridhi Chaudhary’s article “Establishing Hijra Identity: A take on Laxmi Narayan Tripathi’s” traces the discrimination faced by Indian transgenders with reference to Tripathi’s life narrative. However, the fact that Tripathi is a privileged transgender activist to represent the Asia Pacific at the United Nations and having represented her community on several international platforms, including the World AIDS conference in Toronto, is not emphasised.

Thus, the research aims to criticise the homogenised or one-dimensional way in which trans narratives are interpreted. Using these autobiographies, the researcher intends to argue that no individual- in this case, a transgender – can be reduced into a collective entity, because every individual is a combination of different privileged and oppressed identities. When we uncritically categorize the personal narratives of transgender people, there is a high possibility to assume that they face a unified set of common issues. Therefore, the larger concern the researcher intends to find is whether the normative categorisation of the three protagonists, Revathi, Manobi and Laxmi as Indian transgenders capable of bringing in the

real nature of their identities. Is it right to homogenise their experience as similar, just because they share similar sexuality? This notion can be better understood in the words of intersectionality originator Kimberle Crenshaw who in her work “Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color” (2000) states how “identity groups” (Crenshaw 5) like transgenders, gays and lesbians must take into account that individuals are a product of multiple intersecting identities. Therefore, “identity groups” (Crenshaw 5) are not homogeneous as projected by the dominant discourses. She calls this understanding “representational intersectionality” (Crenshaw 7) which questions the homogenous depiction of individuals and groups through media, texts, languages and images which in turn distort the complexity of the group.

From Theory to Praxis: Tracing the Roots of Intersectionality

In the panel discussion titled “A brief report on Intersectionality: Knowing and Doing”, Sumit Baudh discusses the three judicial decisions under Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964, which laid down the foundation for intersectionality. The first act is DeGraffenreid v. General Motors, which decided that Black women could not be given a separate legal category. They have to place themselves either in the sex category or in the race category. A similar understanding also emerged in the judicial decision of 1976, which stated that Black women experiences are similar to that of white women or a Black man. The judicial decision of 1983 by Moore V Hughes Helicopter also failed to provide legal recognition to the double oppression faced by black women in terms of race and gender. This gap gave rise to the theoretical framework of intersectionality, which gave voice to the unique experience of black women who face oppression in terms of both gender and race.

The article “Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality Identity Politics, and Violence Against Women of Color” traces the origin of intersectionality. The concept of intersectionality was coined by Kimberle Crenshaw. However, it can be argued that the

theoretical content of the concept was formed before the actual coining of the term, more specifically in black feminists' attempts to criticise the universalization of white, middle class women's perspective in feminist theory and politics. Through this theory, Kimberle Crenshaw, a black feminist, points out the failure in US anti-discrimination law, which did not take into consideration that black women are victims of both gender based and race based violence. Therefore, Crenshaw points out the need for a theoretical framework like intersectionality, which acknowledges multiple intersecting identities of individuals. She states, "I consider how the experiences of women of color are frequently the product of intersecting patterns of racism and sexism, and how these experiences tend not to be represented within the discourse of either feminism or antiracism." (Crenshaw 1243)

Crenshaw also gives a metaphorical explanation for the failure to acknowledge the doubly oppressed experience of Black women. She compares the theory of intersectionality with traffic intersection as a site of discrimination. In her analysis, she has used speeding cars to portray the different axes of discrimination. According to her study, in this traffic intersection, a black woman who is injured by two cars which signifies race and gender respectively is denied treatment only because one car that caused the injury cannot be identified. This metaphorical analysis aims to critique the unjust way that justice is imparted, favouring a privileged few, while negating the suffering of others.

Central to the development of black American standpoint feminism, Collins 1990's work, *Black Feminist Thought: Knowledge, Consciousness, and the Politics of Empowerment* points how the social categories of gender, race and class are interlocking systems of oppression, joined together in a matrix of domination. Therefore, the work calls for the emergence of a theoretical framework, which does not separate the working of gender, race, class, ethnicity etc. In the words of Collins "Each system need the others in order to function" (Collins 2). Using these pointers, the study claims that the social categories such as gender,

class, race and ethnicity work in mutually constitutive ways, which is considered to be the defining theoretical core of the concept of intersectionality,

Thus, intersectionality became a framework to criticise the hegemonies in white feminism, which failed to acknowledge the double oppression faced by the women of colour. Likewise, theorists like Maxine Baca Zinn, Bonnie Thornton Dill and Maria C. Lugones attempt to point out the flaw in feminist theory for its universalising tendencies on domination faced by women. They advocate ‘multiracial feminism’, an intersectional theory to examine structures of domination, specifically the importance of race in understanding the social construction of doubly marginalised identities.

While Black women are a subject of intersectionality in its origin, that does not limit its applicability to black women or to women in general. Scholars have mobilized intersectionality to engage multiple axes of difference—class, sexual orientation, nation, citizenship, immigration status, disability and religion. The following discourses seem to elucidate this idea.

The work *(Re)Reading Intersectionality and Identity in the Discourse on Marginalized Black Men* (2000) by Keisha N. Lindsay shows how black women are not the only victims of the interlocking system of oppression; black men are also affected by it.

Along the same line, Mason’s work *Leading at the Intersections: An Introduction to the Intersectional Approach Model for Policy & Social Change* (2001) further extends the scope of the theory by saying that most studies conducted on the violence against the lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) community have ignored the intersections among race, class, and gender. Therefore, there arises a need to acknowledge the multiple levels of issues faced by the sexual minorities.

Though intersectionality has extended its scope to multiple categories and target groups, the theory is largely treated as a western discourse. Responding to this common

misconception, this study demonstrates an application of intersectionality in the Indian context. While the concept of intersectionality continues to be widely talked about and deployed by a range of rights and development practitioners and academics in India, various scholars have also interpreted, used, praised and criticized it to different degrees. Therefore, studies more specific to the Indian context of class, caste, gender and sexuality will be discussed below.

The emergence of intersectionality in India can be contextualised with reference to the panel discussion titled “A Brief Report, Intersectionality: Knowing and Doing” held on 17 August 2015 at New Delhi.

Nivedita Menon a professor at Centre for Comparative Politics and Political Theory criticise intersectionality as a theory that travelled widely mainly because of funds from the UN and international NGOs. For Menon, intersectionality is useful for governments but not in feminist spaces. She stated that though Crenshaw used intersectionality to make law more sensitive and sharp, yet a huge body of scholars from the UK has argued that the use of intersectionality concretizes categories. Therefore, the same disadvantage will be carried out when this framework is adopted into Indian academia.

This understanding of intersectionality by Menon is challenged by feminist scholar Mary John who argues for the applicability of intersectionality to feminism in India. Taking a contrary position, she states that she has not encountered intersectionality even in its most diluted form in Indian policy documents. Indeed Menon, does not provide any concrete examples of the so-called governmentalisation of intersectionality in India. She further states that the exclusion of Dalit Muslims and Dalit Christians from the definition of Scheduled Caste highlights why intersectionality is needed and important. To her, intersectionality is not the solution to any issues but a tool to problematise the unnoticed reality.

Another panellist Anita adds to John's discussion on how the government needs to embed intersectionality in their policy framework. She justifies her stance using the example of the Rohtak rape case whose victim was a mentally challenged woman. Anita asks why despite the intellectual impairment of the raped woman, the case failed to evoke the same outrage as the 2012 gang rape in Delhi. By asking this, she points out how the intersectional nature of disability and gender was virtually absent from law and, sadly, even feminist politics. Therefore, she proposes intersectionality as a better framework to understand issues involving multiple discriminations.

Along the same line, activist Nandita Gandhi states how intersectionality has been a rather valuable concept for the women's movement in India. She recalled how in the Mathura rape case, the victim's identity as poor and tribal was not taken into account in feminist debates. Through this example, she highlights how intersectionality refers to the ways race, class, gender, ethnicity, sexual orientation, ability, status and other markers of differences intersect to inform individual realities and lived experiences.

Likewise, Syeda Hameed justifies how intersectionality recognises that individuals and groups are shaped by multiple and intersecting identities. She compares her personal experience of being a Muslim, an educated woman who does not wear the hijab. However, the same categories are not applicable to her neighbour Abu Fazl who is also a Muslim woman. Fazl being a poor, illiterate, differently abled woman further marginalise her identity. Likewise, the three protagonists, Revathi, Manobi and Laxmi, despite sharing similar sexualities, there lies huge differences between them in terms of their familial background, educational status, class, geographical location and so on.

A common thread that the researcher can trace in the above-mentioned studies is that they propose intersectionality as a framework to understand individual identities as pluralistic

and heterogeneous in nature. Therefore, the research intends to propose intersectionality as an apt framework in understanding the diversified nature of trans identities.

With this pluralistic take on education, the study intends to justify the heterogeneity prevalent in educational institutions, which in turn leads to heterogeneous subject formations. To be more specific, the three protagonists – Revathi, a school dropout; Manobi, an MPhil scholar and academician; and Laxmi, a postgraduate, are the products of different educational institutions that have varying ideologies. There seems to be striking differences among them, not only in terms of their familial background but also in terms of education. Therefore, categorizing them under the common identity of a transgender is rather a flawed enterprise.

This chapter intends to examine certain questions of relevance. Can the life experiences of the three protagonists, irrespective of their varied educational backgrounds and career opportunities, can be analysed using a common lens? What are the similarities and differences between the ways in which the three protagonists experienced their educational environment? What aspects of this environment, as defined by the protagonists, help or hinder them in terms of talent identification versus rejection, encouragement versus harassment, career opportunities versus stigmatized profession?

In order to answer these questions, the chapter intends to compare the varied experiences of the protagonists from their different educational setups: Revathi as a school dropout, Laxmi as a postgraduate, and Manobi as an MPhil scholar and India's first transgender principal. With this comparative study, the research will elucidate the significant differences among the protagonists based on their education and career opportunities. The educational experiences of the protagonists are centred on two topics: positive versus negative educational environment as well as career opportunities versus stigmatized professions.

Positive versus negative educational environment is the first topic of analysis. A developing body of research on trans narratives describes educational institutions as a place of harassment, victimization and invisibility for the trans youth. For instance, the article “Education of Transgenders in India: Status and Challenges” (2016) by Rajkumar states that about 80% of transgender students are subjected to physical and emotional harassment in educational institutions. Sometimes, the harassment is meted out by adults and their peers within the institution, and they rarely experience support by an adult or peer stepping in and stopping the harassment (McGuire et al. 1179). As a result of these negative experiences, most transgender youths are subjected to physical and psychological distress (McGuire et al. 1180).

In adherence to the above-discussed argument, the autobiography *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story* points out the physical and emotional harassments faced by Revathi in her school. The protagonist states how she was verbally abused by her fellow students, who indulged in name calling – ‘number nine’, ‘boy-girl’, ‘female thing’, ‘female boy’ and ‘Ali’ – because of her feminine behaviour. This ill treatment of Revathi can be better understood in the words of Higgins:

For many LGBT young people homophobic and trans phobic bullying are serious issues that not only limit and prevent the formation of a positive identity but hinder them from feeling safe, supported and affirmed for who they are in school. (Higgins 77)

In addition to the victimization in school, Revathi also experienced a lack of support from the educators within the school. The protagonist says how, in her school, she was often punished for unmanly behaviour. She states, “I think I was punished not just for being distracted, but also because I spoke like a girl, holding my body coyly like one” (14). The

autobiography also narrates an incident where she was openly humiliated by her PT teacher for not being masculine:

Since I did not play boys game, I got punished by the PT teacher too. He would box my ears and yell, ‘Are you a girl or what? Pull your trousers down, let me check.’ He would make as if he was going to strip me and I would start crying. (7)

Along with the teachers’ rude attitude towards young Doraisamy (who later become Revathi), continued discrimination and violence from the peer group is another important reason for the poor participation of Revathi in educational activities. The following lines from the autobiography seem to substantiate this idea: “I was fed up with being teased, and besides was not doing well in my English classes. I stopped going to school regularly” (10). If Revathi were immersed in a positive environment, there might have been a chance of her excelling in studies. However, the indifference and discrimination she faced in school made her opt for the hijra culture for acceptance. In accordance to this, the article “National School Climate Survey: The experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender youth in our nation’s schools” states,

Schools nationwide are hostile environments for a distressing number of LGBT students, the overwhelming majority of whom routinely hear anti-LGBT language and experience victimization and discrimination at school. As a result, many LGBT students avoid school activities or miss school entirely. (Kosciw et al. 214)

The lack of emotional support and guidance in educational institutions towards a transgender student like Revathi is what makes the school a hostile environment for non-heteronormative gender behaviour. These kinds of discrimination are often seen as the result of a clash of perspectives among parents and professionals in terms of accepting a non-heteronormative gender identity. For instance, in her book *The Spirit Catches You and You*

Fall Down, Fadiman (1997) documents the resentment, anger and frequent misunderstandings that occurred among professionals and family members, who failed to accept a Hmong child living in the United States. Similarly, in the case of Revathi, both her family members and the professionals at school failed to understand her identity, which is different from theirs. This gap has alienated, tormented and forbidden Revathi from actively participating in the educational activities.

However, this is not the case with the other trans women protagonists, Manobi and Laxmi. Their life experiences cannot be homogenized and analysed using Revathi's negative experience. Though one cannot negotiate the low or no tolerance attitude towards sexual minorities in educational institutions, it is important to acknowledge the existence of institutions with a positive and safe environment for transgenders. This kind of positive environment includes caring and accepting adults, anti-bullying and harassment policies, and education of the school staff and students about transgender youth's needs. These factors foster positive psychological outcomes and promote academic achievement for trans students (Greytak et al. 47). While there is a long standing history of oppression within schools regarding queer and transgender issues, there is also a rich, vibrant and creative history of advocacy, activism and significant social change, which ought to be acknowledged. There are schools that specifically address the issues of sexual orientation and gender identity in policies to reduce the harassment of LGBT students (Kosciw et al. 216).

For instance, in the case of Manobi, despite knowing her real identity, her teachers chose to encourage her to excel in her studies. They made her realize that education is the only way through which she can fight against the patriarchal gender norms. She states:

I was known to be a good student, something even the teachers at school could not deny. So they tried their best to ignore this bit as an aberration and egged me to study harder and harder, as if that was the only way I could find emancipation. (32)

As she proceeds further with her higher studies in the science stream, she received the help of encouraging peers like Indra and Mainak Mukhopadhyay, medical college students from R.G. Kar Medical College in Kolkata. The constructive feedbacks received from them helped Manobi get rid of her false assumptions about her own sexual status. She realizes that it is natural and normal to be a transgender. These peers further advised Manobi not to deviate from studies in the hope of undergoing the sex-changing operation at a very young age. They strongly made her believe that she can undergo the operation once she became independent and started earning by herself. It is this guidance which made Manobi focus on her studies, rather than getting distracted by the realization of her sexual identity. She states,

I did not let my awakening sexuality affect my intellect; I would work hard to stay at the top of my class. I realized this was the only way by which I could win this unequal fight. (11)

Besides education, Manobi's teacher also encouraged her talents and interests. Despite young Somanath (later Manobi) being interested in a supposedly feminine act like dance, the teacher allowed her to be a part of it.

In those days no middle-class family would send their boys to learn dance... Anyway, I would see the girls dance and pick up the step. The teacher noticed this and picked me for a role in a cultural show. (13)

Though Manobi faced discrimination in her undergraduate college, Rishni Bankim Chandra College, her identity was the least botheration in a progressive place like the JU. She states, "For progressive JU, my sexual alignment did not matter at all! I was just another student who had come to the university in her quest for excellence and that was the primary concern" (55).

Eventually, this acceptance and encouragement both in school and college life had a cathartic effect on Manobi. These kinds of positive reinforcement added to her privilege of becoming India's first transgender principal.

A similar favourable situation was faced by Laxmi, who states, "In patriarchal, misogynistic cultures such as ours, dancing is seen as a womanly pursuit" (4). However, Laxmi was allowed to learn dance under the guidance of a professional dancer, Baby Johnny. This acceptance and encouragement was a starting point for Laxmi's career as a dancer.

Moreover, the "don't-care" (112) attitude of Mithabai College gave the sense of freedom and liberation which she longed for. Even after entering the college in female attire, with lipstick and long fingernails, her peers did not seem to be bothered by this. Despite her feminine appearance, her positions as a dance master and a model coordinator remained undeterred. It was this acceptance and freedom that contributed to the career upliftment of Laxmi. Her autobiography states thus:

I also started to wear my sexuality on my sleeve. I usually went to college in men's clothes, for I was still a man, but sometimes I picked up courage and landed on campus in female attire.... I was having a good time, and, surprisingly, no one sniggered at me. Perhaps, it had to do with the devil-may-care ethos of Mithibai College – anyone could do anything here. (31)

Furthermore, like Manobi, she also got the help of educated adults like Sangita Sethi, who introduced her to Ashok Row Kavi, the NGO organizer for homosexuals. It was through Ashok that Laxmi got to know that she is normal and therefore eligible to lead a normal life:

No, my child, you are not abnormal. You are absolutely normal. What is abnormal in the world around us? They simply don't understand us... Finish your studies, and don't give up dancing. Come to me after you pass your SSC exams and I will explain everything to you. (11)

It is this kind of guidance and emotional support that Revathi conspicuously lacked. Therefore, she adopted the hijra culture, through which she hoped to become a real woman. Unlike Laxmi or Manobi, Revathi got poor support from her peers, who made her think that becoming a hijra was the only way to be her real self. The autobiography states:

I was told that it was not all that easy to become a woman. Only if I went to Mumbai and Delhi stayed for years with those who wore saris and had undergone operation, could I hope to become one. (19)

The point here is not to sympathize with Revathi by comparing her uneducated status with the privileged side of Laxmi and Manobi. However, the objective is to identify the similarities and differences among these trans women in terms of their educational background. For instance, for Manobi, education was a tool to overcome the adversities regarding her sexual identity. Though she faced a certain level of discrimination both in her school and college, she also enjoyed the support of few peers and educated adults. She states, “I became the butt of ragging in the initial days... But the girls stood by me like solid peers” (42). On the other hand, in the case of Laxmi, education was primarily a means to secure employment. Though she faced sexual exploitation by her brother’s friends during her school days, however, she managed to establish herself as a dance master with the support of her school teachers. Even before passing her SSC exams, she was an established dancer. She gives this credit to her dance teacher Baby Johnny, whose words – “In order to be respected by others, one had to first respect oneself” (25) – inspired Laxmi to start her own dance class as a means to earn respect and money. Furthermore, the “don’t-care” attitude of her college mates encouraged her to further pursue a career as a model coordinator. In contrast, the lack of peer support and teachers’ guidance forced Revathi to drop out of her school. The lack of emotional support and the violence she had to endure both in her school and in her house were the main reasons for her elopement. She states, “I could not bear it anymore, this pain

and hurt that wracked my body and mind... I decided that it would not do for me to continue to live in my parents' home" (33).

From this, one can realize the differences among the three trans women protagonists in terms of peer support and adult guidance. For these reasons, it is rather inappropriate to homogenize their experiences as a collective whole, without acknowledging the differences that exist among them.

The difference in career opportunities available to the three protagonists is the second topic of analysis. Occupation is often associated with an individual's identity, which reflects the position of that individual in a society (Delliswararao and Hangsing 12). Education and skills play a pivotal role in enhancing the employment and economic opportunities for an individual. The article "Socio-cultural Exclusion and Inclusion of Trans-genders in India" states that according to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Child, 1989 (UNCRC) article 29, "the education of the child shall be directed to the development of the child's personality, talents and mental and physical abilities to their fullest potential" (Delliswararao and Hangsing 13). This shows how education serves as an important element in enhancing an individual's talents and career opportunities.

However, the article "Approach Paper on Education and Employment Opportunities & Challenges for Transgender" declares that transgenders are one of the marginalized and vulnerable communities lacking proper education (Rajeshand Naved 13). Majority of the population is uneducated or undereducated, thereby necessitating their exclusion from participating in social, cultural, political and economic activities. According to the Indian Census 2011, there are around 4.9 lakh transgenders in the country. Among them, only 46% are literate (Delliswararao and Hangsing 17).

Hence, most transgenders are forced to earn their livelihood through sex work or prostitution. However, this is not the fate of the entire community. Most importantly, this is

not the sole criterion which can be applied to all the three protagonists taken for study. In spite of these discriminations, some transgenders also work in reputed places: for instance, Manobi Bandyopadhyay working as a principal in a government college in West Bengal, Laxminarayan Tripathi being the president of the NGO DAI Welfare Society, and Revathi being a prominent member of Sangama, an NGO operating for the welfare of sexual minorities. The point here is not to identify the privileged transgenders, but to question the homogenous categorization of the community. While defining the nature of occupations of the three protagonists – Revathi, a hijra cum activist; Manobi, an academician; and Laxmi, a dancer and an NGO's president – the homogenous othering of the trans identity is subjected to scrutiny.

A brief analysis of the different occupations taken up by the protagonists will be useful in studying the differences among them in terms of their career opportunities.

The protagonist Revathi forms the first point of analysis. Due to confusions regarding her own sexual identity, Revathi was not able to actively participate in studies. Therefore, she failed in the SSLC examination. Even her family members declared, “If you think you’ll do well, I will send you to school again. Otherwise, come and help out with the lorry” (15). As a result, as a tenth-class dropout, she was engaged in the profession of a lorry cleaner. Eventually, she realized that becoming a hijra was the only way to be her real self. As a hijra, she was expected to take up the profession of begging. She states thus:

Every morning, the pottais would leave to ask money from shopkeepers. They went in a group to different areas called bazaars. After they were done with collecting money from a bazaar, they divided the collection amongst themselves. (44)

Revathi says that as a hijra, “going and begging in shops was my occupation” (93). In her early twenties, she longed to fulfil her sexual needs. However, being a hijra, she became a prostitute to do so. She says:

I did not like doing sex work, but now found myself doing it. I wanted to experience sexual happiness, but I found myself having to treat sexual experience as a work. (106)

Eventually, there came a time when Revathi became fed up of the physical violence she had to face as a prostitute. She lived in a ghetto, had multiple clients who treated her almost like an animal, was arrested by the police and raped by a gangster. In the end, she decided to return to her parents. However, without a proper means of earning for her daily needs, she almost felt like a burden to her entire family. After undergoing the sex-changing operation, she wasn't even allowed to indulge in her previous profession as a lorry cleaner, a supposedly masculine job. Therefore, in utter frustration, she uttered the following lines: "I had not even passed class 10. Who would give me a job? Who could I possibly ask?" (128). With this attitude, she returned to prostitution, the only livelihood option available for her. It was only after meeting her three educated chelas (daughters), Mayuri, Famila and Rithu, she realized how docile she was and submitted to the tyrannies of the hijra culture. Unlike her, the three educated transgenders did not indulge in begging or suffer the hardships of the ghetto lifestyle. In fact, it was Famila who introduced her to Sangama, an NGO operating for the welfare of sexual minorities. Here, Revathi became an office assistant; she realized that prostitution and begging are not only the livelihood options available for hijras. She argued with her fellow hijras by saying, "For generations all we have been able to do is begging or sex work. How much longer should we have to do this? ...We want to acquaint the world with our lives, and we wish to live like others. That's why I am going to work" (242). It is only after taking up this profession that she started living in an apartment, attending festive occasions as a guest, travelling with ticket, or in her words, she became "one among the many women" (243).

However, the hardships faced by Revathi when she was a part of the hijra livelihood was not faced by her fellow hijra Laxmi. It was her postgraduate status which gave her a sense of upper hand over the other hijras. Even for her guru (mother) Lata, it was a shock that “a boy from a good family, who was college-educated and stylish, should opt to be a hijra” (44). Therefore, she was given the freedom of being Raju in her house. She states, “I felt relieved that I did not have to wear my hijrahood on my sleeve. I did not have to disclose my status as a hijra to anyone unless I wanted to” (44). Moreover, it was her educated status that made Laxmi the president of the DWS, a social organization for the welfare of hijras. When two of the prominent members of the DWS, Shabina and Priya, left, Lataguru encouraged Laxmi to take up this profession, because of her educated status:

After their exit, Lataguru called me and said, ‘So what shall we do now? Who will look after this voluminous work? I have no education and will not be able to run an organization about which I know next to nothing. But you are educated. If you agree to take on the responsibility of running the DWS, it will survive, or else it will close down.’ (61)

After becoming the chairman of the DWS, she entered Kamatipura, Mumbai’s red light area, not as a prostitute but as a delegate. “Work took me to Kamatipura, Mumbai’s notorious red-light district. I could have gone there as a prostitute. Instead, I was going there as a delegate” (64). As a chairperson of the DWS conference, she was invited to a roundtable conference in Mumbai, on the status of HIV and AIDS in India. Apart from this, she was also invited to international conferences held in Toronto and the United States.

Her profession as a dancer and artist gave her an entry into The Netherland Transgender Film Festival held in Amsterdam. She states, “I took the city of Amsterdam by

storm, not just as a hijra, but also as a dancer. I conducted dance workshops that were very popular with the city's young" (99).

Moreover, despite Lataguru's advice to lead a secluded life in the hijra lifestyle, she openly talked about her life to the press and published photographs of her. Though this was opposed by many of the older hijras, she states, "But my chelas stood by me. They were proud of me because I was educated and had a mind of my own. So what if I break all the rules?" It is this sense of emancipation and power associated with her educated status that made Laxmi to battle or break the system that acts as a hindrance to her individual freedom.

An even more different perspective is offered by the educated transgender Manobi, who set out to justify how not all transgenders need not become a hijra. As an educated transgender, she considered herself far more privileged than her friend Jagadish, an uneducated hijra cum prostitute. She states:

Jagadish was a school dropout but that was because her family couldn't afford to educate her. With her sharp mind she would have outshone many, I am sure. But life was not kind to her. In many ways I consider myself far more fortunate than transgendered people like Jagadish. (75)

As a postgraduate student in a liberal institution like the JU, she became a writer with the guidance of Pabitra Sakar, a Bengali linguist. Eventually, after enrolling for an MPhil course in the JU, Manobi became a part-time lecturer at the Sri Krishna College, where she was given respect by all professors, despite knowing her real self. Eventually, she found a permanent job at Patulia Boy's School, where her feminine disposition aroused a lot of curiosity in the neighbourhood. She states, "They found it funny that a person whom they would have loved to call a hijra had actually managed to bag a teacher's job at a reputed school" (68).

From a school teacher, she further got promoted to a lecturer's position at the Vivekananda Satavarshiki Mahavidyala and eventually became the principal at Krishnagar Women's College.

Unlike the fellow hijras Revathi and Laxmi, she did not have to bear the hardships of the hijra culture nor fight back against it, because she was not even a part of it. As an educated transgender, she almost led a life free of stigmatized professions. Meanwhile, Revathi, in her young age, became a beggar and prostitute, the only available options for hijras. On the other hand, the hijra Laxmi chose to fight against the occupational and behavioural norms associated with hijras. Her status as an educated hijra offered her the privilege of becoming a DWS chairman. Thus, the three protagonists share differences in terms of their educational background, which in turn has a huge impact on the job opportunities available for them.

An intersectional analysis of their life narratives with the marker of education brings forth the differences that exist between them. Just because the three protagonists have similar sexualities, it does not mean that their lives should be similar and have the same experiences. The understanding that emerges is that not all transgenders can be categorized as a collective other. As rightly pointed out in the article "The Normative Value of Virginia's Vision of Difference" by Courtney Megan Chill, it is important to acknowledge the reality of differences among individuals belonging to similar social categories, like that of transgenders.

In order to address this research gap, the researcher has selected three Indian transgender life narratives for analysis – A. Revathi's *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story*, Laxminarayan Tripathi's *Me Hijra, Me Laxmi* and Manobi Bandyopadhyay's *A Gift of Goddess Lakshmi*. Using these selected texts, the study has criticised the commonplace

reductionist attitude towards the community, by acknowledging the differences among transgender individuals.

The study has critically engaged with an intersectional framework and justifies it as an apt framework to attain a holistic understanding of the selected autobiographies. Because the previous studies on these autobiographies analysed them only through the travails of gender, oppression of transgenders versus heteronormativity. Placing gender as the prime cause of the protagonists' (Revathi, Manobi and Laxmi's) subjugated experiences may obscure the effects of other systems of oppression by other power structures. Therefore, the researcher has used an intersectional framework to highlight the importance of acknowledging the heterogeneous nature of transgender identities.

In conclusion, the study acknowledges the multifaceted nature of these discourses (education) that shape the lived reality of the protagonists. In short, to fully comprehend the individual experiences of the three trans women, one must seek to understand that their experiences are interconnected and reliant on one another. A failure to do as much often not only results in a misconstrued understanding of the lived experiences of the protagonists, but also limits and confines the heterogeneous nature of their trans identities.

This perspective conveys that individuals' lives cannot be understood through examining only one aspect of an identity, in this case, gender (transgender); the family, education, race, class and geography also shape their life experiences. Therefore, a complete understanding of an individual's experiences can be gained only through a thorough inquiry into the multiple dimensions of one's identity.

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